

Human Gait Analysis in a Random Walk Framework

Marina Raglianti, Mauro Bologna, and Bernardo Tellini*, *Senior Member, IEEE*

Abstract—In this paper, we analyze the human walk movement via a combined deterministic-stochastic model built on top of a random walk framework. We discuss how stochastic and deterministic forces combine to determine the act of moving, adopting a Laban Movement Analysis background to categorize different movement classes. In particular, we recall the four qualitative subcategories of the Laban *Effort* (*space, weight, flow, and time*), and we present their main features through some common examples of movement. Major elements of our study are the analysis of random times when there is a walk movement change, the construction of a distribution (waiting time distribution), and the implementation of a dichotomic stochastic force. Later on, we report the observed walk trajectories obtained via an experimental analysis performed in collaboration with a group of volunteers to show, to some degree, the relationship between their walks and the four subcategories of the Laban *Effort*. Finally, we present our model results via simulated trajectories of a virtual character.

Index Terms—Laban Movement Analysis, Random Walk, Stochastic Model.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human movement analysis is a subject of a great attention by the scientific community of several different areas [1], [2], [3], [4]. Among the several studies, only a few focused on the duration of a movement and provided some association between the human movement features and the observed times [5], [6]. Furthermore, if the kinematic analysis can offer advice on the velocity, as well as on the acceleration of the movement [7], [8], [9] it does not provide a clear description of the statistical nature of the interval sequences between observable movement changes. As better detailed throughout the paper, we believe that the analysis of the times at which we can observe a human movement change can contribute toward a deeper human movement understanding.

The Laban Movement Analysis (LMA) is a pillar among movement analysis systems [10], [11], [12]. Developed by the dancer and choreographer Rudolph Laban, [13], the LMA focuses on the process of the human movement, providing a tool for perceiving and describing the motion [14]. Nowadays, LMA finds application in many fields, such as performing arts, dance movement therapy (DMT), robotics, factory work,

psychology, sociology, and other disciplines that incorporate nonverbal body communication. The LMA is a very multidisciplinary powerful means suitable at describing the structural characteristics and expressions of human motion, as a result of the interaction among the mover, itself, the others, and the environment [15], [16], [17].

Along with the LMA description, we present a novel approach aimed at taking into account the random times when a walk movement changes and extracting the time interval distribution characterizing human walking. The idea of a time distribution suggests the use of a stochastic model. Specifically, we will show how to combine deterministic and stochastic components for human movement description within the Laban *Effort* subcategories [13], as well as to simulate a virtual character expressing different movements. We believe that the attempt to describe the human movement cannot be simply the result of a deterministic model. An approach to the human gait analysis via a stochastic process based on a shape space already appeared in [1]. Thus, a random walk-based model is promising to combine both such effects determining the human walk movement.

The structure of the paper is as follows: in Sec. II we describe the theoretical Laban framework, showing some specific movements in association with the bipolar characteristics of the *Effort* subcategories. In Sec. III, we present our model, discussing the conceptual basis and the role of the main parameters. Section IV describes the experimental analysis and, in particular, shows how to get the model parameters from the observed trajectories and measured random times. In Sec. VI, we report the simulated trajectories of a virtual character for different combinations of the *Effort* subcategories, and, finally, we present our conclusions.

II. THE LABAN *Effort* AND ITS SUBCATEGORIES

According to the framework proposed by Irmgard Bartenieff [14], the LMA defines four main categories: *Body*, *Space*, *Shape*, and *Effort*. The *Body* category describes how the movement is organized and sequenced in the body. It describes “what is moving”, how the body organizes itself. The *Space* category describes “where the body moves”, how the mover directs her/his attention onto the environment. *Body* and *Space* are kinematic features and describe the structural characteristics of the movement [18].

On the other hand, the *Shape* and *Effort* categories are more relevant to the qualitative aspects of the movement [19]. The *Shape* looks at the change of the form of the body, about self or to others, “toward where” the body is changing its shape, as a

M. Raglianti is with the Universidad de Tarapacá, Departamento de Educación de la Facultad de Educación y Humanidades, Universidad de Tarapacá, 1010069, Arica, Chile (e-mail: marinaraglianti70@gmail.com).

M. Bologna is with the Universidad de Tarapacá, Departamento de Ingeniería Eléctrica-Electrónica, 1010069, Arica, Chile (e-mail: mauroh69@gmail.com).

B. Tellini is with the Università di Pisa, Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell’Energia, dei Sistemi, del Territorio e delle Costruzioni, Largo Lucio Lazzarino, I-56122, Pisa, Italy (e-mail: bernardo.tellini@unipi.it) - *Corresponding Author.

Fig. 1. Left (right) sequence: strong (light) *weight* movement.

Fig. 2. Left (right) sequence: direct (indirect) *space* movement.

bridge between *Body* and *Space*. Finally, the *Effort* (originally named by Laban *Antrieb* in the German language) reflects the attitude towards the movement, “how the body moves”. The *Effort* concerns what precedes the action, the transition zone between being and acting outward, as a request to satisfy a need. The *Effort* manifests through four different bipolar factors [20]: *weight*, *space*, *time*, and *flow*. The *weight* can be strong or light (Fig. 1), as well as the *space* direct or indirect (Fig. 2), the *time* sudden or sustained (Fig. 3), and the flow free or bound (Fig. 4).

The *weight* primarily relates to one’s relationship with Earth’s gravity, although it has not to be associated with the body weight per se. Our discussion better characterizes the amount of energy spent to activate the movement. A direct *space* expresses an action to move along a straight line, the attraction towards a clear focus, while an indirect *space* is more related to flexible attention to the surrounding environment.

The *time* is concerned with the attitude toward how (sudden or sustained) the person approaches the movement. Thus, the *time* has not to be associated with the time duration of the action but is related to the urgency affecting the quality of the movement and, in our model, to the time to wait for the next observable movement change. Finally, the *flow* characterizes the control of the movement during the action; in our discussion, it indicates a sort of memory of the movement sequence.

Looking at Fig. 1, it is apparent how the body is closer to the ground for the strong *weight* movement, which indicates a body more inclined to fall in gravity in comparison with the light weight movement. Thus, stronger/lighter weight movements imply larger/smaller energy dissipation. A simulation of such a concept is shown in Fig. 1, and analogously for the other subcategories in Figs. 2-4. Consecutive frames are separated by about 0.15 s for all Figs. 1-4. In all the cases, movements are performed by an expert in body language and LMA. Although these images cannot represent the whole complexity of the corresponding movements, it is possible to get the bipolar characteristics of the four subcategories considered.

From the left sequence of Fig. 2, we can observe how the person moves toward an expected goal, while a sense of more indulgence in the space appears in the other case.

The left frames of Fig. 3 simulate a relatively higher urgency in the movement process, while the body seems to indulge in the time in the other sequence.

Fig. 3. Left (right) sequence: sudden (sustained) *time* movement.

From Fig. 4, it is apparent how the movement with free *flow* more randomly interests the space outside the body of the person, while the bound *flow* sequence obliges the body to move within a more controlled space. As we will further discuss in our model, a bound *flow*, implies a sort of body memory, such as the gesture of a twirling dancer requires high movement control, as the result of a long body training.

III. STOCHASTIC MODEL

As known from the literature, Brownian motion can be described within random walk theory as a stochastic process in which a particle moves randomly to the nearest point at equal time intervals. The random walk represents a generalization of the Brownian motion, and it finds applications in many disciplines, among which mathematics, statistical physics, economy, sociology, network science, [21], [22], [23], [24].

The idea of adopting a random walk framework to implement our conjecture arises from visualizing the very classic example of the drunk’s walk, in association with the unpredictable component of human motion. In more detail, the drunk person does not know where he/she is going, and flips a coin at each step to decide whether to go forward or back, right or left; this physically pictures the basic concept of a

Fig. 4. Left (right) sequence: free (bound) *flow* movement.

random walk. Finally, the position of the drunk person after n “decisions” is a random variable. More specifically, for a continuous time random walk, the walker tosses the coin at random times extracted by a time distribution, and, as a consequence, the movement changes happen in a random time sequence.

The proposed model implements a deterministic force in association with the direct *space* component, while models *weight* via a friction coefficient to simulate the energy spent against the gravitational field during motion. The *time* is characterized by a waiting time distribution. A stochastic force characterizes the free *flow* component. It is, however, important to point out that *space* and *weight* are not deterministic per se. Indeed, the randomness of *time* and *flow* reflects into *space* and *weight*, as well as the deterministic component of the movement associated with *space* and *weight* affects the other two subcategories. The adopted strategy implements a combined deterministic-stochastic process. Finally, all the parameters can be identified by observing the human movements, as will be discussed in the following.

Let us now define \mathbf{F} as a force that can exert an action to move the human body, and let us write \mathbf{F} as the sum of the two contributions:

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_d + \mathbf{F}_r \quad (1)$$

where the first term, \mathbf{F}_d , is the deterministic force and \mathbf{F}_r represents the stochastic term. The deterministic component induces motion toward a stable objective, while the stochastic force contributes to a random fluctuation of the movement from a stable trajectory. Gaits characterized by higher and dominating values of \mathbf{F}_d are thus an expression of direct *space* from a point A toward a point B , while higher values of \mathbf{F}_r imply a random walk, an indirect *space*. On the other hand, higher values of \mathbf{F}_r can also be interpreted as an expression of free *flow*, as it will become apparent from our discussion. The stochastic force is modeled as a dichotomic process in our description. As a consequence, \mathbf{F}_r fluctuates between the constant values $\pm\mathbf{F}_0$, with a distribution density of time durations of the two states extracted from a time distribution $\psi(t)$. Thus, the random part can be sketched as a series of “stop and go” separated by a random time interval extracted from $\psi(t)$.

Let us now introduce the force $\beta\mathbf{v}$, which is representative of a friction effect, i.e., of the energy dissipation to exert the motion, or, in other words, of the difficulty of moving against the gravitational field. This term includes the *weight* in our scheme, and higher/lower energy dissipation implies greater/smaller values of the friction coefficient β . Thus, we have:

$$m \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = -\beta\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{F} \quad (2)$$

where $\beta\mathbf{v}$ is the phenomenological quantity representing the *weight*. At a first discussion, we can simplify (2) assuming the term $m d\mathbf{v}/dt$ to be negligible for our analysis, thus writing:

$$\beta\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{F}, \quad \Rightarrow \mathbf{v} = \frac{\mathbf{F}}{\beta} = \frac{\mathbf{F}_d}{\beta} + \frac{\mathbf{F}_r}{\beta} \equiv \mathbf{v}_d + \mathbf{v}_r \quad (3)$$

Indeed, a negligible $m d\mathbf{v}/dt$ assumption means that the stochastic velocity component \mathbf{v}_r does not vary between two consecutive changes of the direction [25]. In more detail, according to such an assumption, the times for the direction changes are small compared to the time intervals between two consecutive changes. Such an approximation should be possibly removed for a person walking in a crowded space.

As a consequence, $\psi(t)$ expresses the time during which the velocity \mathbf{v}_r keeps the value $+\mathbf{v}_0$ or $-\mathbf{v}_0$. More sudden *time* are expected to be associated with more rapid changes, i.e., smaller average time intervals.

In our discussion, the waiting time distribution is assumed to be a Poissonian distribution, and the exponent coefficient is a phenomenological parameter generally dependent on several conditions. We may express it as:

$$\mathbf{v}_r = \mathbf{v}_0 \xi(t) \quad (4)$$

where $\xi(t) = \pm 1$ represents a random fluctuating quantity, thus, generating the values $\pm \mathbf{v}_0$. We may then rewrite (3) as:

$$\mathbf{v} = \frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt} = \mathbf{v}_d + \mathbf{v}_r, \Rightarrow \frac{d}{dt}(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{v}_d t) = \mathbf{v}_0 \xi(t) \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{r} is the position of the walker. Thus, (5) describes a random walker moving with a constant velocity for a random time τ_1 , then changing velocity direction for a time τ_2 , and then again for a time τ_3, \dots, τ_n . The random times are extracted from a Poissonian distribution $\psi(t) = \gamma \exp[-\gamma t]$, where the parameter $1/\gamma$ represents the average time to get a decision.

$$P(x, t) = \frac{1}{2} \exp[-\gamma t] \left[\delta(f_0 t - |x - f_d t|) + \frac{\gamma}{f_0} \times \left(I_0 \left[\gamma \sqrt{t^2 - \left(\frac{x - f_d t}{f_0} \right)^2} \right] + \frac{t I_1 \left[\gamma \sqrt{t^2 - \left(\frac{x - f_d t}{f_0} \right)^2} \right]}{\sqrt{t^2 - \left(\frac{x - f_d t}{f_0} \right)^2}} \right) \theta(f_0 t - |x - f_d t|) \right] \quad (6)$$

is the probability distribution to find the walker at the coordinate x when the walker started at the origin, $P(x, 0) = \delta(x)$. Here $I_n(z)$ is the modified Bessel function of the first kind and $\delta(t - |x|)$ is Dirac’s delta, a function that represents the walkers that never changed the direction of their velocity.

According to statistic theory, the described process is expected to recover a Gaussian diffusion process for a time sufficiently large, or, equivalently, for a relatively high value of γ .

$$P(x, t) \approx \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{2\pi t}} \exp \left[-\frac{\gamma}{2} \frac{(x - f_d t)^2}{t} \right]. \quad (7)$$

At a first analysis, depending on the intensity of the random process, short average times to take a decision can interpret a sense of urgency, as well as an unbound *flow*. In all the cases, such a condition indicates something far from the expression of a well-controlled movement sequence.

Fig. 5. Photograph of the outdoor setting: a 12 m \times 11.6 m area. A red and white ribbon grid defines a mesh of 870 square subelements with 40 cm edge.

On the other hand, relatively small values of γ compared to the intensity of the stochastic process can be more related to sustained *time*, or bound *flow*.

Besides, in the limit of $\gamma \rightarrow 0$, the motion equation writes as:

$$\frac{1}{f_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} P(x, t) + \frac{\gamma}{f_0} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} P(x, t) = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} P(x, t). \quad (8)$$

from which we recover the known wave-equation, as well as we can argue relatively very high average time to get a decision. Indeed, there is not sufficient time for the stochastic process to diffuse. As a consequence, it is apparent an intimate relationship between *time* and *flow* in our model. Although the two subcategories are conceptually different, urgency or rushing [14] are generally competitors of careful actions.

Finally, in our description, the *flow* is related to a sort of memory of the motion, of the previous sequence of foot movements. A relatively bound *flow* is expected to be associated with a smaller stochastic component \mathbf{v}_r , but, in some cases, it can be perceived by the observer as also associated with a longer average time for taking a decision. A random walker that keeps the memory of the previous steps is known in the literature as a persistent random walker [24], which corresponds in our case to a relatively γ small value.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

A preliminary experimental analysis was carried out to observe the walk trajectories associated with different combinations of the *Effort* four subcategories. In Fig. 5, a photograph of the prepared outdoor setting is shown. A 12 m \times 11.6 m meshed area was divided into 870 square subelements of 40 cm edge each. Thus, the adopted spatial resolution in our estimation of the step position and observed spatial trajectory. We chose an outdoor setting with such dimensions to prevent as much as possible from the border effect. Indeed, too much small space constrains the trajectories and limits the efficacy of the analysis. Based on the obtained results, the chosen dimensions appear an acceptable compromise for the present purposes.

We did not apply any sensors to the volunteers during the campaign, and we acquired videos of their walks by a commercial video camera. The time resolution of the video camera was about 33 ms. Because of the limited statistics, we did not report any sex or age classification. Thus, the volunteers are here identified simply as v_1, v_2, \dots, v_5 .

All the volunteers received a generic input for a direct *space*: start the movement from a vertex of the square ($x = -6$ m, $y = 6$ m), and finally, exit the setting from the opposite vertex ($x = 6$ m, $y = -5.6$ m). Then, they were invited to combine such an input: a sudden (sustained) *time*; a bound (free) *flow*; a heavy (light) *weight*. They received no other inputs and no constraints on their performance time, leaving them as much as possible free to interpret their movement.

The observed trajectories are reported in Fig. 6: dimensions are in (m). The upper plots refer to the combined direct *space*-sudden *time* (solid line), -sustained *time* (dashed line), and -bound *flow* (dash-dotted line); the lower figures show the trajectories in association with free *flow* (solid line), heavy *weight* (dashed line), and light *weight* (dash-dotted line). From left to right, the panels refer to: v_1, v_2, v_3 . The analogous trajectories to Fig. 6, are shown in Fig. 7 for v_4 and v_5 . For the sake of readability, the combined case, direct *space*-light *weight*, is shown separately (right plots) for both v_4 and v_5 .

For all the volunteers, results mostly show how the trajectories relevant to sustained *time*, free *flow*, and light *weight* are more dispersed over the square, compared to their counterparts, which show paths much tight closer to the diagonal.

V. RANDOM TIME ANALYSIS

As discussed in Sec. III, the waiting time distribution $\psi(t)$ represents the distribution of the random times at which the walk movement direction changes. An accurate description of what identifies a movement change is a key question for properly defining our subject of investigation. In this section, we further clarify how to get the random step and velocity components and the random times from the measurements reported in Sec. IV. For each subcategory case, we thus combined the data relevant to all the five volunteers to form a single data sheet. Then, we determined the two mean components of the term \mathbf{v}_d of (3) by dividing the total length along x and y by the exit time. It is worth to remark that $v_{dx} \sim v_{dy}$ for all the tests. To get the random components of \mathbf{v}_r , we then proceeded as follows: firstly, we subtracted the average step length from the actual step length, thus obtaining the random step component; next, at each time of observation, i.e., at each step, we divided the random step by the time duration of the step, thus obtaining the random velocity; finally, we got the average of the absolute values of the random components $v_{rx} \sim v_{ry}$.

In particular, we got larger \mathbf{v}_r components for the combined direct *space*-sudden *time*, -free *flow*, and -light *weight* subcategories, compared with their counterparts.

In Fig. 8, we show the waiting time distributions of a virtual character reconstructed from the random time distributions of all five volunteers. Time intervals, i.e., the random times, are those at which \mathbf{v}_r changes its sign, while the parameter γ is evaluated as the inverse of the average time interval. In particular, we can observe a substantial agreement with the assumption of an exponential-like distribution.

In Tab. I, we summarize the experimental parameters relevant to the considered combinations of the *Effort* subcategories. Results show a relatively shorter mean time interval

Fig. 6. Upper panel trajectories: direct *space-sudden time* (solid line), *-sustained time* (dashed line) and *-bound flow* (dash-dotted line); lower panel trajectories: direct *space-free flow* (solid line), *-heavy weight* (dashed line), and *-light weight* (dash-dotted line). From left to right: v_1 , v_2 , v_3 .

Fig. 7. Upper panel trajectories: direct *space-sudden time* (solid line), *-sustained time* (dashed line) and *-bound flow* (dash-dotted line); lower panel trajectories: direct *space-free flow* (solid line), *-heavy weight* (dashed line), and *-light weight* (dash-dotted line). From left to right: v_4 , v_5 .

Fig. 8. Reconstructed waiting time distribution for a virtual character.

($1/\gamma = 1.2$ s) for the direct *space*-sudden *time* performance, while for all the other cases, average time intervals are approximately between 3 s and 4 s. Furthermore, higher v_r appear for the combined direct *space*-free *flow* and -light *weight* compared to their counterparts.

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL PARAMETERS IDENTIFIED FROM THE OBSERVED TRAJECTORIES; v_d STANDS FOR $v_{dx} \sim v_{dy}$, v_r FOR $v_{rx} \sim v_{ry}$, RESPECTIVELY. REPORTED SUBCATEGORIES ARE COMBINED WITH A DIRECT *space*.

	$1/\gamma$ (s)	v_d (m/s)	v_r (m/s)
sudden <i>time</i>	1.22	1.33	0.52
sustained <i>time</i>	3.75	0.31	0.40
bound <i>flow</i>	3.17	0.31	0.20
free <i>flow</i>	3.17	0.34	0.90
heavy <i>weight</i>	3.90	0.30	0.19
light <i>weight</i>	4.05	0.35	0.66

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we simulate the trajectory of a virtual random walker. As we will show, the results are promising, and, in principle, the model can be extended to simulate more complex movements.

In Fig. 9, the simulated trajectories are shown for all the considered cases. At first glance, the results show a clear difference for the combined subcategories direct *space*-sudden *time*, -bound *flow*, and -heavy *weight*, compared with the other cases, and they appear in substantial agreement with the observed trajectories of the five volunteers.

It is possible to notice how the simulated trajectories show abrupt changes in direction (formation of tip points). However, this is not an intrinsic limit of the model but just a consequence of the adopted approximations in the current version. An underlined gray fit line is also reported to help the reading of the simulated paths.

Furthermore, the simulated direct *space*-sustained *time*, -free *flow*, and -light *weight*, all express more sense of indulgence in the space, i.e., more occupancy of the area as a result of a higher stochastic component relatively to the intensities of the other two parameters γ and v_d . Besides, the observer perceives less possibility of repeating the very same sequence for the simulated sustained *time*, free *flow*, and light

weight. This can find, for example, confirmation, if we imagine observing a healthy adult or a little child, both attracted by a deterministic force toward an objective. Both the adult and the little child will define a trajectory, but it is expected that if they are asked to repeat their movement, the little child should deviate more evidently from its previous path.

VII. CONCLUSION

We analyzed the human gait via a combined deterministic-stochastic model based on a random walk framework. Along with a Laban Movement Analysis background, we recalled the main features of the four *Effort* subcategories, and combined deterministic and stochastic forces to represent the movement qualities associated with the Laban *space*, *weight*, *time*, and *flow*. As a major aspect of our discussion, we pointed out how the time distribution has a central role in the model characterizing the randomly extracted instants when the walk movement changes. We then reported the results of an experimental analysis performed in an outdoor setting with volunteers walking on a plane. In particular, we included the trajectories performed by five volunteers as a result of different combinations of a direct *space* with the other subcategories. Furthermore, we discussed the identification process of the model parameters from the measured trajectories, and we presented the outputs of our model via randomly extracted trajectories of a virtual character. The obtained results showed a substantial agreement with the observed trajectories, confirming the capability of the adopted model to discern the considered human gaits and how the presented approach of random quantities can contribute to shedding light on novel aspects of this topical issue.

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Fig. 9. Simulated trajectories. From left to right: (upper panels) direct *space-sudden time*, *-sustained time*, *-bound flow*; (lower panels) *-free flow*, *-heavy weight*, *-light weight*.

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